

TRENDS AND PROSPECTS FOR EDUCATING THE YOUNGER GENERATION

¹Z.Ismailova, ²Lee Sanhseoug, ³O.R. Jamoldinova, ⁴S. Yu. Ashurova

¹ Professor of Tashkent Institute of irrigation and agricultural mechanization specialists -
National Research University.

¹e-mail: z.ismailova@tiame.uz

²Professor of Keimung College University

³Professor at Tashkent State University of Uzbek Language and Literature named after Alisher
Navoi

⁴ Professor of the Institute for the Development of Professional Education

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10655147>

Abstract. *The article covered scientific and pedagogical aspects of the state policy, its priorities, essence and essence of the education of young generation in Uzbekistan in the years of independence, as well as the use of modern pedagogical and information and communication technologies and the Internet, scientific and technical information.*

Keywords: *modernization, priority directions, legal-normative documents, spiritual-moral and physical harmony, preschool educational institutions, innovative technologies in education, scientific and technical information, pedagogical mechanism.*

INTRODUCTION

The fundamental reforms carried out in Uzbekistan during the years of independence are aimed at protecting the interests of the society and the state, upbringing prosperity of the people for prosperity and prosperity, development and improvement of the democratic state of law based on national and universal values. Significant work is underway to support young people, protect their rights and interests, create conditions for their education and occupation, and help them to take up the role of life. Indeed, the Strategy for Action on the Development of the Youth in the Republic of Uzbekistan in 2017-2021, proposed by President S.Mirziyoyev, said: "Improving the state of the youth policy is physically sound, spiritually and intellectually developed, independent thinking, loyal to the Motherland, raising their social activity in the process of educating young people with a positive attitude, deepening democratic reforms and building civil society " [1.4 / 5] Lake is one of the priority directions of development.

METODOLOGY

In the implementation of this goal, the legal and regulatory basis for the upbringing of physically and morally and spiritually mature youth was improved. In particular, the Laws of the Republic of Uzbekistan "On Education" (1997), "On National Program of Personnel Training" (1997), "On Prevention of Iodine Deficiency Diseases" (2007), "Guarantees of Child Rights" (2008) (2010), "On the prevention of immune suppression and juvenile delinquency" (2010), "On the distribution and consumption of alcohol and tobacco products" (2011), "Human immunodeficiency diagnostics (2013), "On guardianship and sponsorship" (2014), "On physical education and sport" (2015), "On state youth policy", "On prevention of the spread of HIV infection" (2016) and other laws, Decrees, Resolutions and Orders of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan, Decree, Decree and Decree of the Cabinet of Ministers of the Republic of Uzbekistan serve as the methodological basis of the work being done in this area. Result:

– improving the content of education in accordance with international requirements, strengthening the material and technical basis of educational institutions, management and modernization of management, the use of innovative pedagogical technologies and ICT in

educational process is a factor of this process. Of course, the management of the educational process is based on the principles of democratization of the state power and administration. Creation of the scientific and theoretical basis of management, definition of conceptual pedagogical bases, development mechanism of its implementation, ensuring the existence, factors, principles, content, form, methods, means of integrity of the integral pedagogical system, ensuring inheritance, impartiality and integrity in management special attention was given to the use of information technology in the management, modeling and management;

- maintenance of regularity of improving the content, forms, methods and means of education, state educational standards, curriculum, textbooks on the basis of time requirements, widespread introduction of modern communication and information technologies in the educational process, the effective use of advanced pedagogical technologies yields results;

- creation of a system of advanced training and retraining of highly qualified personnel in accordance with the requirements of globalization and competitiveness, democratization and liberalization processes in the world, is one of the most important requirements for building a democratic, civil society. system for each vapor. Also in the centuries-old work on the preparation of young people with modern, competitive professional secrets, on the basis of the most advanced achievements of science, innovative technologies, their preparation to professional activity are carried out;

- strengthened the legal framework for the protection of the spiritual and physical health of young people, their protection against harmful habits, the legal basis of the quality of Internet services, the improvement of the organizational and legal mechanisms of democratic institutions in ensuring the effectiveness of the educational process;

- an important measure to further improve the mechanism of pedagogical cooperation of the school, family, civil society institutions, which is the basis of education and training, expand the scope of their tasks, strengthen interaction with educational institutions, improve organizational and methodological support, - Establishing and implementing them in consistent practice demonstrates their effectiveness in the education of young people;

- serves as an important tool for improving the content, forms and methods of child education and upbringing in the educational institutions, extracurricular educational institutions and specialized educational institutions;

- youth in need of social support, support for young people in need of social protection, formation of social activity in them, complex research of conceptual scientific foundations of bringing up and raising a healthy offspring, development of scientific and theoretical ideas and their implementation in educational process are conducted in our country. as one of the priority issues of the reform;

- one of the most important stages in the formation of a perfect human being is the availability of a high standard of training competitive staff, ie the emergence of a unified system of academic lyceums and professional colleges, their material and technical basis in line with world standards;

- teaching young people to foreign languages through the introduction of innovative forms and methods of teaching modern pedagogical and information and communication technologies, mastering the system of training specialists who can speak fluently in these languages and their widespread use of achievements of world civilization and world information resources, Partnerships, opportunities for dialogue and opportunities.

RESULTS

Who can teach the world of pedagogical science, what do we teach, how to read, what can we achieve? The answer to these questions is always relevant. To find a complete answer to these questions, you need to clearly define the perspectives for increasing the effectiveness of your teaching. Today's rapid development requires the use of modern pedagogical and information-communication technologies and the Internet, as well as scientific and technical information. We would like to highlight the peculiarities of these two perspective pedagogical aspects, which are the means of effectiveness of the youth education. The goal is to form a free and independent, independent and strategic mind-set spiritually and physically capable person who will further integrate our republic into the international community. First of all, it is a requirement to pay special attention to introduction of innovative pedagogical technologies in educational process.

Innovative approach to the teaching and learning process envisages the organization of educational process through innovative pedagogical technologies. Research shows that the effective use of innovative pedagogical technologies is based on innovative approach to teaching and learning process. We have discovered that innovative pedagogical technologies have the following features in ensuring the future of education and upbringing of the younger generation:

- is being carried out on raising competitive, competent experts in foreign languages, occupying a number of professional secrets with advanced knowledge and skills of advanced technical and technological knowledge, which makes a worthy contribution to the further integration of our republic into the international community, spiritually, physically, independently and independently, important measures will be implemented successfully;
- in the context of the use of modern teaching materials, the educational process is carefully planned, predicted, designed and delivered, the result is guaranteed;
- the subjects of educational process are rational use of the existing scientific-theoretical, methodical resources, spend time, pedagogical creative activity;
- the social-moral healthy environment in the community will be sustainable, its innovative management will be achieved;
- takes the responsibility to constantly improve their professional skills and scientific-pedagogical activity on "Theoretical and practical use of modern pedagogy, information and communication technologies and their effective application in the learning process using global Internet, multimedia systems and distance learning";
- the teacher and the student fully demonstrate their abilities, intellectual capabilities and capabilities as subjects in the course and out of the classroom work;
- to have knowledge, skills and knowledge in the field of theoretical knowledge, professional competence, initiative and augmentative education of the teacher, psycho-psychological and educational science, practical training;
- Pedagogical techniques and technology combine together with teachers and students to achieve educational and learning objectives, to achieve high results;
- the interest of pedagogical activity, ensuring the active participation of the class, the full realization of the students' knowledge, the ability to realize their abilities, the efficient use of time, the high motivation of both subjects to work on themselves;
- the creative pedagogical activity of the pupil and the teacher lies in the basis of innovative pedagogical technologies. Therefore, the student's level of development is high.

Compliance with the basic concepts of innovative pedagogical technologies, ensuring the success of the educational process, ensures its effectiveness. That is, they include: pedagogical

principles, factors, interactive methods, innovative technology and tools for education and upbringing, innovative management. It is quite natural that the use of innovative pedagogical technologies, based on the scientific and technical resources of the curriculum, the nature, goals and objectives of the subject, the essence of the didactic process, the capabilities of the subjects, the motivation, the environment and the environment.

DISCUSSION

The global development of the XXI century is accompanied by scientific and technical information, widely and intensively, the development of telecommunication technologies, the diversity of innovative technologies, cooperation in science and technology, education and production, the vital necessity of the electronic governance system, Globalization leads to the development of younger generations. The peculiarity of this process is that the need for young people to exchange information within and outside the country is growing day by day.

In the use of scientific and technical information systems in the education of youth, the following materials are important:

- information about the spiritual aspects of information available on the achievements of science and technology in our country and world scale;
- adverse effects of the 21st century threatening information-psychological security;
- scientific and technical innovations reflected in the press and mass media and their human capital formation information on the spiritual foundations;
- using the global Global Public Communication Tool (OAC), the use and retrieval of national information technologies and resources, providing fast and up-to-date information;
- the use of spiritual and educational aspects of the information reflected in information and telecommunication means and systems;

There are also sources that threaten the education of young people, such as nationalism, chauvinism, localism, ideological dependency and expansionism, imperialism, terrorism, radicalism, extremism, illegal migration, human trafficking, drug abuse, etc. Continuous education the use of scientific and technical innovation in the fight against such destructive ideas in the formation of youth spirituality in the system, serves as an important factor in their forming innovative ideas.

The formation of youth morale requires the advent of the negative effects of concepts such as "popular culture", "information confrontation", "information war", "information pressure" and "information crisis". Therefore, it is time for the minds of young people to understand the rebellious ideas of interested people or groups based on these ideas. First of all, it is desirable to pay particular attention to the role of national values as well as the role of universal values. In this context, scientific and technical information includes conferences, educational seminars, competitions, talk shows, web-seminars, media resources, spiritual, educational, popular, artistic and documentary films, social TV and radio broadcasters, posters, booklets, meetings, roundtables, photo albums, workshops, discussions, interlocutors, etc. are key to the benefits.

CONCLUSION

Studies show that the above priorities in the upbringing of a mature human being in Uzbekistan are gradually evolving from the very first days of independence, guaranteeing the outcome, prospects of accuracy, and the effectiveness of their work. Work on this area, which is being implemented in the formation of a brilliant human being, also defines the prospects of reforms in education in our country. Thus, in raising the effectiveness of spiritual, moral and physical education of young people:

– improvement of the content of education on the basis of achievements of world civilization and world information resources, strengthening of material and technical basis of educational institutions, increase of effectiveness of training of modern, competitive pedagogical personnel;

– Improving the content of teaching, ie improving the state educational standards, curriculum, textbooks, teaching materials and methodologies on the basis of international best practices, the use of modern pedagogical and information and communication technologies in education and the Internet, scientific and technical information, is a pledge of lifting;

– Moderation of the system of retraining and advanced training of pedagogical and managerial personnel in all levels of the education system, and the wide implementation of modern management of education is an important factor in ensuring the quality of education.

REFERENCES

1. The Constitution of the Republic of Uzbekistan. (2012). Tashkent: "Uzbekistan".
2. The Law of the Republic of Uzbekistan "On State Youth Policy" (2016). Tashkent, Justice ".
3. Laws of the Republic of Uzbekistan "On Education", "On the National Program of Personnel Training" (2020).
4. The Law of the Republic of Uzbekistan "On Physical Culture and Sports" (2015).
5. Law of the Republic of Uzbekistan "On guarantees of the rights of the child" (2008).
6. The law of the Republic of Uzbekistan "On the prevention of juvenile delinquency and offenses" (2010).
7. Law of the Republic of Uzbekistan "On Restriction of Distribution and Use of Alcohol and Tobacco Products", 2011.
8. Law of the Republic of Uzbekistan "On prophylaxis of iodine deficiency diseases" (2007).
9. Law of the Republic of Uzbekistan "On prophylaxis of micronutrient deficiency among the population" (2010).
10. Law of the Republic of Uzbekistan "On guardianship and sponsorship", (2014).
11. Decree of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan dated February 7, 2017 "On the Strategy for the Further Development of the Republic of Uzbekistan", PF-4947 (Annex 1, Strategy for Action on Development of the Republic of Uzbekistan in 2017-2021).
12. Mirziyoev, Sh. (2018). The Decree of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan "On the State Program" Yoshlar - kelajagimiz "of June 27, 2018." Xalq so'zi "newspaper, 28.06.2018.
13. Mirziyoev Sh. (2018) DP - 3907 of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan from August 14, 2018 "About measures on education of children morally and morally and physically healthy, raising the quality of education system to a qualitatively new level" The Hellenic Word newspaper, 15.09.2018.
14. United Nations High Education of the 21st Century (1998), UNESCO's "Higher Education Reform and Development" Program (1995)
15. A. Musurmanova, Z. Ismailova, R.Xamroev "Improving the Competence of Future Vocational Education Teachers based on Modular-RatingEducation" International Journal of Engineering and Advanced Technology (IJEAT), ISSN: 2249 – 8958, Volume-9 Issue-1, October 2019
16. A. Musurmanova, Z. Ismailova "Pedagogical mechanisms of development of initiative at students of universities". European Journal of Research and Reflection in Educational Sciences, (**EJRRES**): Volume 8 Number 2, 2020 Part II. ISSN 2056-5852

17. Zukhra Ismailova, Ruzimurot Choriev, Aynisa Musurmanova, Mahfuza Aripjanova “Methods of training of teachers of technical university on Advanced training courses” Journal of Critical Reviews ISSN- 2394-5125 Vol 7, Issue 5, 2020
18. Zuxra Karabaevna, Aynisa Musurmanova, Rustam Xamroevich “Improving the Competence of Future Vocational Education Teachers based on Modular-Rating Education” International Journal of Engineering and Advanced Technology (IJEAT) ISSN: 2249 – 8958, Volume-9 Issue-1, October 2019
19. T. Narbaeva, A. Musurmanova “Priority Areas Of Spiritual, Moral And Physical Education Of Youth In The Family” Ilkogretim Online - Elementary Education Online, 2021; 20 (3): pp. 1648-1656 <http://ilkogretim-online.org> doi: 10.17051/ilkonline.2021.03.187